

EVALUATION OF PROCESSED GROUNDNUT (*ARACHIS HYPOGAEA*) CAKE MEALS IN THE FEEDING OF CLARIID CATFISH, *CLARIAS GARIEPINUS*, FINGERLINGS.

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ABSTRACT

Groundnut cake (GNC) meal is an important source of dietary protein for domestic animals with a cost advantage over the conventional animal protein sources used in aquaculture feed production. It would be useful to evaluate the effects of GNC processing methods on the density and nutritional values of processed GNC meals. The use of processed GNC meals in the diets of *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings was evaluated. Seven iso-proteic and iso-caloric diets were formulated, replacing fish meal with roasted and boiled GNC meals, each at three inclusion levels of 30%, 35%, and 40%. Diet I is 100% fishmeal, Diet II is 30% roasted GNC meal, Diet III is 35% roasted GNC meal, Diet IV is 40% roasted GNC meal, Diet V is 30% boiled GNC meal, Diet VI is 35% boiled GNC meal and Diet VII is 40% boiled GNC meal. Results showed that the crude protein content of GNC meals was 40.5% and 40.8% in boiled and roasted GNC meals respectively; the lower protein content for processed GNC meals might be due to heat denaturation of the seed protein, with boiled GNC meal being more adversely affected. The mean weight gain of fingerlings fed roasted GNC meals ranged between 5.29 – 5.64 while for boiled GNC meals, it was between 4.60 – 5.22. Generally, fish performed better when fed diets containing roasted GNC meals, than boiled GNC meals, and compared favorably with fish fed fish meal based diet. Body mass increase, total feed increase, protein efficiency ratio and specific growth rate by *C. gariepinus* fingerlings in all diets, showed no significant differences, suggesting that processed GNC meals could partially replace diets for *C. gariepinus* fingerlings without adverse consequences. This study showed that processed GNC meals could partially replace fish meal up to 30% without significantly influencing fingerling growth and health. It is recommended that the use of fish meal as the main basal ingredient for fingerlings could be discontinued, since GNC meal was a cheaper alternative, and could replace fish meal up to 35%, without any significant adverse effects on the fingerling performance.

KEYWORDS: *Clarias gariepinus*, Fingerlings, Groundnut cake meal, Nutrient utilization, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) cake meal is an important source of dietary protein for domestic animals, and has a cost advantage over the conventional animal protein sources used in aquaculture feed production. It has been considered among others as a good substitute for fish meal Ezenwa (1982), Ekanem (2003).

Groundnut cake is an abundant, cheap and easily available plant protein source that is high in crude protein content (40-45%). Feed ingredients used for fish rearing are usually chosen on the basis of their nutrient content (proximate composition), cost, availability and acceptability by fish, as food Eyo and Ezechie (2003). The protein content of GNC meal has sub-optimal amount of cystine and methionine, although the first limiting amino acid in GNC is lysine Jackson *et al.* (1982).

When GNC meal is used in a diet with a high cereal composition, adequate supplementation with animal protein is necessary, to ensure that the deficiencies of vitamin B₁₂ and calcium would be corrected (Fagbenro *et al.*, 2000). There are many constraints on the use of legume seeds in fish feeding; these include the presence of anti-nutrients such as trypsin-inhibiting tannin, Lemaglutannins, phytase, anthocyanin, unacceptable taste or flavour, and the long and tedious cooking/processing time. Many methods have been employed to reduce or remove these problems

associated with legumes in fish feed. The effects of sprouting, cooking, roasting, autoclaving, soaking and germination on legumes had earlier been reported Egwaikhide *et al.* (2005).

In Africa, *Clarias gariepinus* is of some great economic importance, as an esteemed fish food with a higher dressing percentage and consumer preference than most cultured fish species in freshwater Balogun and Fasakin (1996). It is hardy and can be bred in captivity.

However, the provision of adequate, cheap and nutritive feed has hindered the development and profitability of catfish farming, especially in developing countries. The possibility of supplementing or replacing one meal with another in the aquaculture industry exists. Several authors (Ekanem 1992, Balogun and Fasakin 1996, Fagbenro *et al.*, 2000, Arimoro 2005, Eyo and Ezechie 2003, Oresegun *et al.*, 2004, Oharei 2005) have successfully carried out these replacements. But there is a lack of information on the use of processed GNC meals in fish feed. Therefore, this study was conducted to evaluate the effects of two processing methods (roasting and boiling) on the density, nutritional values of processed GNC meals, and growth performance of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location of investigation

The experiment was conducted in Akure, Ondo-State, Nigeria. Akure is located in the humid forest region of southwestern Nigeria. The town has tropical climate with two distinct seasons, namely: rainy season (April - October) and dry season (November - March). Temperature ranges vary from 21°C during the rainy season to 28°C during the dry season, while humidity is relatively high. It is located between longitudes 5°22' and 5°23' East of Greenwich Meridian and latitudes 7°15' and 7°17' North of the equator. The town is mainly on upland zone, rising above 250meters above the sea level.

Preparation of GNC meals

Raw groundnut seeds (2 kg) were purchased from Divine Mills, Akure, Nigeria. The seeds were manually selected to remove dirt, after which they were washed, and dried at 60°C for 24 hours AOAC (1990) methods in a domestic/kitchen oven. When dry, they were divided into two equal batches.

Boiled sample

One batch of raw groundnut seeds was boiled at 90°C for 30 minutes, sieved to remove water, and then sun-dried at ambient temperature (25°C) for two weeks. Thereafter, the seeds were ground in a hammer mill, sieved (25 mm wire mesh), and stored in an airtight container prior to chemical analysis.

Roasted sample

The second batch of raw groundnut seeds was roasted in a sauce pan containing sand that was heated over a Bunsen burner. The sample and sand were roasted for 30 minutes, stirring occasionally using a wooden spoon. The roasted sample was allowed to cool for 20 minutes, after which the seeds were ground with a hammer mill, sieved (25 mm wire mesh) and stored in an airtight container, awaiting chemical analysis.

Chemical analysis

The proximate composition (moisture, crude protein, crude lipid, crude fibre and total ash) was performed using standard AOAC (1990) methods.

Diet formulation

Based on the nutrient composition of the feedstuff (Table 1), seven isoproteic and isocaloric diets were formulated as presented in Table 2. Diet I, serving as the control diet contained 100% fishmeal with 0% GNC meal, whereas the other six test diets (II to VII) contained GNC meal (roasted or boiled) as partial replacement for fishmeal (Table 2) providing 30%, 35% and 40% of total protein. The description of diets was as follows: I, 0% GNC meal; II, 30% roasted GNC meal; III, 35% roasted GNC meal; IV, 40%, roasted GNC meal; V, 30% boiled GNC meal; VI, 35% boiled GNC meal; and VII, 40%, boiled GNC meal. The lipid content of all diets was adjusted with 2.5% groundnut oil while gelatinized cornstarch 3.0% was supplemented to adjust gross energy content (Fagbenro *et al.*, 2000). After mixing all ingredients together, the prepared starch was added. This helped to hold the ingredients as well as being a

source of gross energy. Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) was added at 10 g per kg, as a non-nutritive binder, (Fagbenro *et al.*, 2000).

Table 1. Proximate composition (%) of feedstuff.

Nutrient	Fishmeal	Maize	Roasted groundnut cake	Boiled groundnut cake
Crude protein	65.67±0.01	9.13±0.01	40.75±0.01	40.52±0.04
Crude lipid	13.10±0.01	2.70±0.02	9.81±0.01	9.67±0.01
Crude fibre	-	2.42±0.01	4.25±0.03	4.33±0.02
Ash	4.36±0.04	3.61±0.01	5.31±0.02	5.29±0.01
Moisture	7.60±0.02	7.24±0.01	7.01±0.02	7.31±0.02
*NFE	9.27±0.01	74.90±0.02	32.87±0.02	32.88±0.02

*NFE (Nitrogen free extract), calculated as 100-(Moisture + crude protein + crude lipid + ash).

Table 2. Composition of the experimental diets (dry matter basis, %).

Ingredients	Fishmeal 100%	Roasted GNC 30%	Roasted GNC 35%	Roasted GNC 40%	Boiled GNC 30%	Boiled GNC 35%	Boiled GNC 40%
Fishmeal	57.0	26.0	36.9	42.0	26.0	36.9	42.0
GNC meal	0.0	20.5	18.1	18.0	20.5	18.1	18.0
Maize	33.0	43.5	35.0	30.0	43.5	35.0	30.0
Vit-min premix	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Bone meal	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Groundnut oil	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
CMC	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Starch	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Calculated	Nutrient	Composition%					
Crude protein	40.30	39.86	39.85	39.74	39.87	39.71	39.78
Crude fibre	2.08	5.56	4.12	4.02	5.66	4.32	4.47
Crude lipid	8.12	8.99	7.78	7.62	9.74	8.38	8.27
Ash	4.75	5.45	5.34	5.22	5.40	5.31	5.10
*NFE	44.75	40.18	43.05	43.05	39.40	42.28	42.55

*NFE: Nitrogen free extract.

The feedstuff was blended in a Hobart A120 food processor (Hobart, Troy, OH, USA), and the resultant mash was moistened and pressed through a 3-mm die. The resulting strands were oven-dried at 45°C for 24 hours, (Fagbenro1999), broken into pellet lengths of 1.0 cm, and stored in airtight plastic containers at ambient temperature. Water stability of pellets was determined in triplicate samples (Wood 1987).

Experimental fish and systems

Hatchery-bred fingerlings of *C. gariepinus* (mean mass: 3.69±0.01g) were procured from the Agricultural Development Project (ADP), Akure, Nigeria, and randomly allotted to 15 plastic circular tanks (50-litre capacity) at 20 fingerlings per tank. The fish were acclimated to experimental conditions for seven days, and starved for 24

hours prior to the feeding trial Ekanem (2003). Water from a borehole was passed through a circulatory filtration system before entering the experimental tanks to filter away impurities and to aerate the water.

Each diet was fed to *C. gariepinus* fingerlings in triplicate tanks per treatment to apparent satiation twice daily (9am to 4 pm) for 56 days. Fish mortality was monitored daily. Individual fish in each tank was weighed at the start of the experiment and weekly for the appropriate indices (Steffens 1989).

Table 3. Performance of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings fed processed groundnut cake meals dietary inclusion for 56 days.

Diets							
	Fishmeal 100%	Roasted GNC 30%	Roasted GNC 35%	Roasted GNC 40%	Boiled GNC 30%	Boiled GNC 35%	Boiled GNC 40%
Initial mass g	3.81 ^{ab}	3.86 ^b	3.96 ^b	3.40 ^a	3.76 ^{ab}	3.64 ^{ab}	3.40 ^a
Final mass g	10.49 ^c	9.50 ^b	9.25 ^b	8.80 ^{ab}	8.98 ^{ab}	8.54 ^{ab}	8.00 ^a
Mean Weight Gain g	6.68 ^c	5.64 ^{ab}	5.29 ^{ab}	5.40 ^{ab}	5.22 ^{ab}	4.90 ^a	4.60 ^a
Average Daily Growth	0.12 ^b	0.10 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.10 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.08 ^a
Body Weight Increase %	175.33 ^b	146.11 ^{ab}	133.59 ^a	158.82 ^b	138.83 ^a	134.62 ^a	135.29 ^a
Specific Growth Rate	0.44 ^b	0.39 ^{ab}	0.37 ^a	0.41 ^{ab}	0.38 ^a	0.37 ^a	0.37 ^a
Protein Efficiency Ratio	2.78 ^c	2.62 ^c	2.17 ^{ab}	2.56 ^b	2.01 ^a	2.00 ^a	1.89 ^a
Total Feed Intake g	3.45 ^c	3.33 ^b	3.12 ^{ab}	3.28 ^b	2.89 ^{ab}	2.81 ^a	2.69 ^a
Daily Feed Intake g	0.029 ^b	0.025 ^b	0.021 ^a	0.022 ^a	0.020 ^a	0.021 ^a	0.021 ^a
Survival %	96 ^b	97 ^b	87 ^a	91 ^b	89 ^a	90 ^a	95 ^b

Growth performance parameters

Mean weight gain (MWG): mean weight gain was estimated according to the method of Pitcher and Hart (1982).

MWG = mean final weight – mean initial weight.

Average daily growth (ADG) = mean weight (MWG)/ rearing period (days)

% Body weight increase (%BWI): this was obtained according to Stuart and Hung (1989).

% BWI = mean weight gain (MWG)/ mean initial weight X 100

Specific growth rate (SGR): this was estimated from the logarithmic difference between final and initial mean weight of fish per time (Hogendoorn 1980).

$SGR = \frac{\log W_f - \log W_i}{t} \times 100$

Where W_f = mean final weight

W_i = mean initial weight

t = rearing period (days).

Feed gain ratio (FGR): $Tf / W_f - W_i$

Where Tf = total amount of diet fed to a tank for the rearing period divided by the number of fish in the same tank.
Survival: this was monitored daily by examining experimental tanks each morning and dead fish were removed and counted. At the end of every week, fish in each tank were counted.

$$\% \text{ Survival} = N_f / N_i \times 100$$

Where Nf = final number of fingerlings per tank

Ni = initial number of fingerlings per tank

$$\text{Daily weight gain (DWG)} = \text{body weight gain/ rearing period (days) i.e. } W_f - W_i / t$$

$$\text{Total feed intake (TFI)} = \text{feed weight/ no of fish per tank}$$

$$\text{Daily feed intake (DFI)} = \text{TFI/ } t$$

$$\text{Protein intake (PI)} = \text{protein content} \times \text{DFI}$$

$$\text{Protein efficiency ratio (PER)} = \text{ADG} \times \text{PI}$$

Statistical analysis

All data obtained were subjected to one-way ANOVA test ($P < 0.05$). Where ANOVA revealed significant differences, Duncan's multiple-range test (Zar 1996) was applied to characterize and quantify the differences between treatments using Statgraphics 5 Plus Package for Windows (Mannugistics Inc. and Statistical Graphics Corp, Maryland, US. 1998).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proximate composition of GNC meals

Table 1 shows the results of proximate composition of differently processed GNC meals. Crude protein content of GNC meals was 40.52% and 40.75% in boiled and roasted GNC meals, respectively. These values fell within the range of 40-55% as reported by Pillay (1993) and 40.7% to 41.2% reported by Fagbenro (1999). The lower protein content recorded for processed GNC meals may be due to heat denaturation of the seed protein with boiled GNC being more affected. Heat-treated protein cause irreversible denaturation leading to association and precipitation of the polypeptide chains as high molecular weight compounds, (Wolf 1970). The results showed that boiled GNC meals had measurable lower ($P > 0.05$) dietary protein, lipid and ash than those of the roasted GNC meals. According to Fagbenro *et al.*, (2000), boiling, fermentation and roasting of seeds have affected their nutritional contents. Crude lipid, crude fibre and ash of the processed samples were similar, but were higher than the values reported for maize (*Zea mays*). The data from the present study indicated that processed GNC meals could conveniently be incorporated into the diet of *C. gariepinus* fingerlings. The substitution of fishmeal with processed GNC meals enhanced the energy, ash and fibre profiles of the diets (Table 1). Similar enhancement has been reported by Arimoro (2005) who replaced artificial Stanlor with *Brachionus calyciflorus* larvae in catfish.

Growth performance of fingerlings

Mean weight gain was highest in diet with 30% inclusion of roasted GNC meals and least in diet with 40% inclusion of boiled GNC meal. Total feed intake was least in diet with 40% boiled GNC meal, while it was highest in diet with 30% roasted GNC meal. Protein efficiency ratio was also found to be lowest in fingerlings fed diet with 40% boiled GNC meal while the highest value was obtained in fingerlings fed diet with 30% roasted GNC meal.

Growth performance and nutrient utilization of fish fed on all the treatment diets are summarized in Table 3. The responses of fish to the different diets showed that growth and nutrient utilization were significantly ($P < 0.05$) influenced by the processing methods. Fish fed diets containing boiled GNC meals had significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower body mass, total feed intake, protein efficiency ratio and specific growth rate compared to the control diet. This is evidenced in the proximate composition of the major protein sources in the experimental diets (Table 1). Table 3 shows that the best growth response was obtained in *C. gariepinus* fingerlings fed the control diet (Diet 1). *C. gariepinus* fingerlings fed diets II, III and IV had comparatively similar growth response as those fed the control

diet, although lower. The different processing methods applied on the GNC meals might have led to decreased dietary protein utilization, since the protein had been denatured, leached and vaporized, hence reduced performances, although roasted GNC meal produced better results. According to Emiola and Ologhobo (2006), heat treatments are less effective in the detoxification of tannin, phytate and oxalate in seeds. Roasting appears to be partially effective in inactivating the lectins and trypsin inhibitors. The results obtained in this study affirms that the good performance of fish fed diets containing roasted GNC meal may be due to the processing technique (roasting) compared to boiling to remove anti-nutrients which probably influenced nutrient availability, palatability and utilization of the meals.

Acceptance of the diets was good and fingerlings became accustomed to the diets within the first week because there were no morphological defects observed during this period. Body weight mass increase, total feed increase, protein efficiency ratio and specific growth rate by *C. gariepinus* fingerlings in all diets (Table 3), showed no statistical differences, which suggests that processed GNC meals could partially replace diets for *C. gariepinus* fingerlings without compromising growth and fish health. This deduction is in agreement with observations made by Fagbenro (1999) on the performance of winged bean meals on African Clariid catfish; Eyo and Ezechie (2003), on the performance of rubber meals on *Heterobranchus bidorsalis* and *C. gariepinus*; Arimoro (2005) on the performance of *Brachionus calyciflorus* on *H. longifilis* larvae; and Okoye *et al.* (2006) on the performance of graded levels of sorghum meal on broiler chicks. Each of them discovered no significant differences in the TFI, SGR, PER and BWI of fingerlings fed the test diets and the control diets.

Means with the same superscripts along the same row are not significantly different, according to Duncan 's Multiple Range test.

Fish mortality

It was observed that survival rate was high with the lowest at 87% and the highest was 97%. The fingerlings easily got acclimatized to the test diets and accepted the diets readily without compromising their health thereby reducing the rate of mortality.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study revealed that processing GNC meals can successfully partially replace fishmeal up to 30% without significantly affecting growth and fish health. Replacing fishmeal with GNC meal up to 30% will lower the cost of feeding fish since GNC meal is relatively cheaper than fishmeal which hitherto was used as the main basal ingredient in formulating diets for fish. Under critical fishmeal shortfall GNC meal can be used as main basal ingredient in formulating fish diet, since replacing fishmeal up to 35% GNC shows that fish were still gaining weight. It is recommended that the use of fishmeal as the main basal ingredient could be discontinued, since GNC meal was a cheaper alternative, and could replace fishmeal up to 35%, without any significant adverse effects on fingerling performance.

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FAPOHUNDA Olowumi Oluwafunmilola: Continental J. Fisheries and Aquatic Science 2: 23 - 30, 2008

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Received for Publication: 29/11/2008

Accepted for Publication: 10/12/2008